

Behaviour of Cobaltous Oxide on Heating.

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Hedvall (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, 121, 217) has found that the physical and chemical properties of ferric oxide undergo a change when the oxide is prepared at different temperatures. Prasad and Tendulkar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1403) have also found that the physical and chemical properties of nickelous oxide change remarkably, when the temperature at which the oxide is prepared is raised. These authors have pointed out the importance of these results in the separation of nickel from the nickel-copper matte by the action of dilute sulphuric acid. This paper contains the results of a similar investigation on the properties of cobaltous oxide.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Kahlbaum's extra pure cobalt carbonate, free from iron and nickel, was heated for 2 hours in a silica boat under vacuum to different temperatures in an electric furnace and cooled very slowly. The samples of the cobalt oxide obtained at different temperatures were analysed for cobalt by the electrolytic method. The results obtained are given below.

TABLE I.

Temp.	...	500°	600°	700°	800°	900°
Cobalt (%)	...	76.79	77.55	77.98	78.17	78.47

It appears that cobalt carbonate should be heated up to 900° before a pure sample of cobaltous oxide is formed (%Co in CoO is 78.66).

These samples of oxide, like nickelous oxide, contained some active oxygen which was estimated iodometrically. The amount of active oxygen was found to decrease as the temperature of preparation of the oxide was raised. On applying a correction for this amount of oxygen in the oxide obtained at different temperatures it was found that the oxides obtained at low temperatures did not conform to the theoretical composition.

Like nickelous oxide prepared at low temperature (Prasad and Tendulkar, *loc. cit.*) the samples, obtained at low temperatures, yellow in colour became black when exposed to air. But unlike nickelous oxide, the black colour of the cobalt oxide was not found to disappear when it was treated in an acidified solution of potassium iodide or heated to 500° in vacuum. It is probable that in this case either some different oxide is formed or the attachment of the adsorbed oxygen on the surface of the particles is firm. The low percentage of cobalt obtained in the oxide prepared at low temperatures may thus be mainly due to (i) the adsorption of oxygen by the oxide when exposed to air, and (ii) the occlusion of gases evolved during the decomposition of the carbonate (*cf.* Richards and Rogers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, **15**, 567).

Physical and Chemical Properties of Cobaltous Oxide.

Density.—The oxides prepared at higher temperatures settled in water more quickly than those prepared at lower ones. The experimentally determined densities of the oxides by means of a pyknometer at 28° are given below.

TABLE II.

Temp. (t)	...	500°	600°	700°	800°	900°
d_{40}^{28}	...	4.8	5.28	5.6	5.79	6.15

On plotting d against t , it is found that the curve is represented by $d = 0.3477 t^{0.4223}$.

Solubility in sulphuric acid.—The solubility of cobaltous oxide was measured in 0.1 N-sulphuric acid.

TABLE III.

Temp.	...	500°	600°	700°	800°	900°
CoO dissolved (%)	...	93.35	92.75	83.90	74.65	65.10

It will be seen that the fall in the solubility of the oxide is very rapid as the temperature of preparation is raised from 600° to 900°.

Catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide.—The catalytic effect of cobaltous oxide (*cf.* Nickelous oxide, Prasad and Tendulkar, *loc. cit.*) in the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide was measured in a neutral and an alkaline solution at 30°. The oxide (0.02 g.) was added to 25 c.c. of hydrogen peroxide solution (prepared by tenfold

dilution of Merck's pure 10 volume product) and the rate of decomposition was followed by titrating 2 c.c. of the reaction mixture at definite intervals against $N/100\text{-KMnO}_4$ solution.

TABLE IV.

Decomposition of H_2O_2 in a neutral solution.

Time.	H_2O_2 in terms of $N/100\text{-KMnO}_4$ decomposed by oxide prepared at				
	500°	600°	700°	800°	900°
10 min.	10.0 c.c.	3.0 c.c.	1.20 c.c.	0.50 c.c.	0.20 c.c.
20	15.5	5.0	2.10	0.70	—
30	19.5	7.0	3.10	0.90	0.60
40	23.0	9.0	4.08	1.15	—
50	—	11.0	4.95	1.60	1.00
60	27.5	13.0	5.90	2.00	—
70	29.0	14.0	7.10	2.60	1.20
80	30.0	15.5	—	—	—
Average value of K (Unimolecular constant)	0.0328	0.0086	0.0035	0.0011	0.00067

TABLE V.

Decomposition of H_2O_2 in an alkaline solution.

1.0 C.c. of $0.01N\text{-NaOH}$ added to 25 c.c. of H_2O_2 solution.

Time,	H_2O_2 in terms of $N/100\text{-KMnO}_4$ decomposed by oxide prepared at			
	600°	700°	800°	900°
10 min.	7.5 c.c.	3.20 c.c.	2.00 c.c.	1.2 c.c.
20	10.5	4.50	2.50	—
30	13.0	5.35	—	1.8
40	15.5	6.40	3.60	—
50	18.0	7.30	—	2.3
60	20.0	8.30	4.40	—
70	21.5	9.45	—	2.7
80	23.5	—	—	—

The unimolecular constant K was not found to be constant in this case. On plotting x against t the curve is represented by $x = at^\beta$ in which the value of β is nearly constant in all the four reactions and the value of a is different for different reactions.

Electrical resistance.—The electrical resistance was measured by Ryschkewitsch's method (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1926, **32**, 538) and the specific resistance S was calculated in the manner described by Prasad and Tendulkar (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE VI.

t	...	500°	600°	700°	800°	900°
S	...	3170	5200	7300	9250	9380

It will be seen from the foregoing that the physical and chemical properties of the cobalt oxide change immensely when the temperature of preparation of the oxide is changed. The density and the electrical resistance of the oxide increase and the solubility in sulphuric acid and the catalytic decomposition of hydrogen peroxide decrease as the temperature of preparation of the oxide is raised. This increase or decrease is by no means proportional to the change in temperature; only the electrical resistance increases linearly with temperature but this linear relationship no longer holds as the temperature is raised from 800°—900°.

The action of solid substances in a heterogeneous reaction depends upon the size of the particles of the substance. In the present case, although very great care was not taken to use particles of exactly the same size in each experiment, yet the results show a remarkable change in the action of the oxide as the temperature of preparation is altered.

The various causes which are responsible for inducing the inactivity in the oxides as the temperature of the preparation is raised have been discussed by Prasad and Tendulkar (*loc. cit.*). Attempts are now being made in this laboratory to account for this induced inactivity.